

Poster: Qualia Exploitation of Sensing Technology (QuEST) for Vehicular Network Optimization

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Abstract—**Qualia-based Exploitation of Sensing Technology (QuEST) is a dual process framework that leverages what is known about human neurophysiological and neuropsychological processes to create an artificial cognitive exoskeleton functioning similarly to the human mind. In this paper, we present a quick QuEST overview and a visionary approach using QuEST methods that can improve cognitive V2V network resistance to hacking. QuEST tenets and designs have been used successfully in cyber security, facial recognition, and cancer detection; thus V2V information security in the open internet context can be enhanced via QuEST. Of note, QuEST’s focus is on intelligence amplification (IA) versus artificial intelligence (AI) and developing a machine architecture which closes the loop between human and machine.**

Keywords—*cognition, information fusion, intelligence amplification, security.*

I. INTRODUCTION

ACCURATE and timely exploitation and dissemination of relevant sensor, semantic, statistical, and graphic information is critical to secure internet of things (IoT) functionality. IoT has been extended to vehicular network (VN) systems, which aim to improve transportation efficiency via information sharing between vehicles. Unfortunately, IoT devices can be exploited by hacker organizations to perpetrate denial of service and other attacks on internet nodes [1], websites and databases. Thus, security in VN systems is of concern and a currently open research area [2], [3]. To combat this problem, development of an intelligence amplification (IA) guardian between VN networks and the open internet is recommended. Data transfer can best be guarded in a robust manner if a dual systems representational approach is used. This permits quick reflexive responses to expected information transfers and more deliberative ‘conscious’ responses to unexpected or bogus directives to VN systems. This dual process system resembles the way the human brain handles incoming information and thus facilitates trust. The human brain is composed of circuit nodes called microcircuits that are specialized for processing down-sampled sensory data into perceptions (qualia) which are then associated into whole brain-spanning networks composed of compound-qualia from which contextual meaning is calculated and appropriate actions generated [4], [5], [6]. V2V networks could be

organized into specialized processing nodes including: public safety, traffic congestion, and car-to-car data, as well as VN node and agent interactions with the open internet. This will provide the context for hacker signal identification and isolation.

II. QUEST

The human brain down-samples from a high dimensional visual, auditory, and memory information space as a matter of course. Just so, intelligence amplification machines (IAMs) must down-sample from a high dimensional data space, whether we are talking about information flowing between VN vehicle agents, nodes, and networks or the IoT. Since it is impossible to anticipate all possible hacking events relevant to successful VN security, information management and routing, new approaches are necessary to permit secure and effective VN operations in the IoT context.

To meet this need we propose utilizing a relatively new approach: Qualia-based Exploitation of Sensing Technology (QuEST). The overarching goal of QuEST is to design an IAM [7], [8] that can effectively partner with human operators (facilitating tight coupling between human and machine). QuEST is composed of three key modules: 1) agents (sense and act upon an environment), 2) qualia (agent-experienced data and constructs derived from sensed data), and 3) a dual-process framework that posits two qualitatively different yet related processing modes (see Figure 1).

A. Recent QuEST-based Implementations

QuEST concept implementations have been instantiated in various applications, including Breast Cancer detection [9], cyber [10], and facial recognition [11]. In these problems, algorithms were employed to consider features in a general-to-specific sense, e.g. shape, texture, spatial, spectral, and interest points, in a fusion hierarchy. Each algorithm was first considered as a QuEST agent; agents were connected through various links with such connections used to extract context [11]. Agent internal representation was improved through adaptive feedback with methods termed “adaptive gallery” and “multi-look” [11]. Adaptive gallery architecture changed library dimensionality by removing low scoring matches, multi-look considered alternating library images if and when new information became available.

